

NucBench: A Benchmark Framework for Evaluating Multimodal Large Language Models in Nuclear Engineering

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ABSTRACT

Widespread adoption of Large Language Models (LLMs) in scientific and engineering applications is an increasing ease of access, capability of complex reasoning, and capacity to process large amounts of data [1]. However, models are still prone to hallucinations, outdated information, weak reasoning and other logical errors [2]. Error mitigation is required in industries where safety and accuracy are critical, as with nuclear engineering. Typically, the performance of these LLMs is benchmarked through the time-consuming practice of comparing their results to those of computationally expensive physics simulators resulting in comparisons on LLM performance for strictly quantitative results [3]. This paper introduces NucBench, a comprehensive benchmark designed to evaluate multimodal Large Language Models (LLMs) in nuclear engineering using a streamlined process. Unlike generic AI benchmarks, NucBench integrates quantitative, qualitative, and image-based assessments derived specifically from reactor operator fundamentals, academic examinations, and two-phase flow regime classification. As a case study we demonstrate the validation of three frontier and widely used (at the time of this publication) models; GPT-4.1, Claude 3.7 Sonnet, and Gemini 2.5 Pro, which were tested under deterministic and stochastic temperature settings to quantify both accuracy and response variability. GPT-4.1 achieved the highest quantitative accuracy (95 %) on deterministic runs, while Claude 3.7 Sonnet showed the greatest consistency across open-ended tasks. Image-based evaluations revealed reliable performance for churn flow but limited capability in differentiating complex regimes such as slug and Taylor. The benchmark establishes a transparent foundation for evaluating LLMs in nuclear applications, enabling reproducibility, explainability, and domain-specific performance tracking.

Keywords: Nuclear engineering, Large language models, Benchmarking, Two-phase flow, Reactor operator exams

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of Large Language Models (LLMs) has transformed artificial intelligence (AI) from linguistic assistants into general-purpose cognitive engines capable of complex reasoning, multimodal perception, and domain adaptation. Whether the nuclear engineering community embraces it immediately or not, the integration of such models into research, education, and operational decision-making is becoming inevitable [4]. Across industries, LLMs are being embedded in mission-critical systems, from medical diagnostics and drug discovery (e.g., BioGPT, Med-PaLM 2 [5,6]) to aerospace mission planning (NASA's "Watson-AI Flight Control Prototype" [7]) and financial risk modelling (BloombergGPT [8]). These examples illustrate both the opportunities and challenges of deploying AI systems whose internal reasoning remains largely opaque.

In this rapidly shifting landscape, nuclear engineering (NE) faces a dual imperative: harnessing LLM capabilities for analysis, training, and safety documentation while ensuring the same level of rigor, traceability, and validation expected of any computational tool in a regulated environment. Unlike other engineering disciplines, NE applications demand quantitative fidelity, procedural correctness, and predictable behaviour under uncertainty—criteria that generic AI benchmarks fail to assess. Frameworks such as MMLU [9], GSM8K [10], and BIG-Bench [11] evaluate general reasoning or common-sense knowledge but do not capture the intricate numerical reasoning, physical-law consistency, and multi-modal interpretation required in reactor physics, thermal-hydraulics, or radiological protection. In the case of BIG-bench and GSM8K, indirect leakage of data used to benchmark models to the models is possible since many of the tasks used in their benchmarking are publicly available on the internet. NucBench’s two-tier benchmark design, as covered in section 2.1, prevents this leakage. As well, NucBench employs temperature sampling compared to BIG-bench where most examples were sampled greedily with a temperature of zero [11].

To address these gaps, the NucBench initiative was conceived as a domain-specific benchmark suite tailored for nuclear engineering. NucBench evaluates LLM performance across three principal categories:

Textual question answering using operator fundamentals and academic examination datasets;

Reasoning under uncertainty, by systematically varying model sampling temperature to observe stochastic reliability; and

Visual understanding through classification of two-phase flow regimes using experimental image data.

By integrating these heterogeneous tasks, NucBench offers a statistically robust and reproducible framework for quantifying both *accuracy* and *consistency*, two indispensable indicators of reliability in safety-critical AI systems. It also establishes a reproducible testing ground for future fine-tuned or hybrid models that combine symbolic physics reasoning with LLM-based perception, ultimately supporting safer and more transparent AI adoption within nuclear engineering.

2 METHODOLOGY

The NucBench framework integrates structured datasets, controlled evaluation procedures, and statistical reporting metrics. Three principal datasets were curated to represent authentic challenges encountered by nuclear professionals and students: (i) the *General Fundamentals Exam* (GFE) for reactor operators, (ii) *undergraduate nuclear engineering examinations*, and (iii) a *two-phase-flow image dataset* for visual classification tasks. Each dataset was selected to test a different reasoning mode, conceptual, quantitative, or perceptual, thereby providing a holistic assessment of language-model competence. Note that the questions used in task (ii) are not accessible online; therefore, they could not have been part of any model’s training dataset.

Table I. Summarized Datasets Included in the NucBench Private Evaluation Set.

Task	Domain			Format	Size
GFE Operator Exam	PWR/BWR Fundamentals			Multiple-Choice	4,292 Qs
Undergraduate Exam	Reactor	Physics,	Thermal-	Quantitative &	108 Qs
	Hydraulics,	Fuel Cycle		Qualitative	
Two-Phase-Flow Classification	Thermal-Hydraulics			Image Classification	947 Images
Radiation Spectrometry	Radiation Measurements	Detection	and	Images & data files	120 files

The datasets are stored in a modular repository containing qualitative, quantitative, and multimodal folders with unified metadata schemas. Each dataset instance is saved as a JSONL record and indexed via a registry file that defines canonical paths and schema validation rules. This structure ensures

reproducibility and ease of access for benchmarking, while maintaining strict version control of content additions.

2.1 Two-Tier Benchmark Design

To preserve fairness and prevent data leakage into training pipelines, NucBench employs a two-tier design:

- **Public GitHub (Development Split):**
Contains schemas, loaders, baseline scripts, and a limited “dev” subset with labels. This split enables debugging, fine-tuning of evaluation pipelines, and public contribution without exposing the gold-standard questions or labels. The link to the public GitHub repository can be found in Appendix A.
- **Private Evaluation Set (Gold Split):**
Remains fully encrypted and served only through a secure evaluation gateway. No direct downloads are allowed; users submit model outputs via an API for scoring. The NucBench API defines how benchmark tasks interact with the model and how performance is measured. The backend computes accuracy, variance, and confidence intervals, returning summary metrics only.

This controlled evaluation model deters overfitting and ensures that leaderboard results reflect genuine generalization rather than memorization.

2.1 Repository Expansion and Roadmap

The repository will expand to include publicly available datasets and controlled-access industrial data to benchmark emerging multimodal AI systems under realistic nuclear-engineering scenarios. The following roadmap illustrates the incremental evolution of the platform:

1. **v1.0 (Now):** Public dev split + schemas; evaluation gateway for gold tests; standardized JSON reports.
2. **v1.1:** Parameterized quantitative problem generators and randomized thermal-hydraulic image augmentations performed server-side. Support of programmatic Python benchmark tasks with custom metrics, direct interactions and queries to models.
3. **v1.2:** Container-based *compute-to-data* path allowing users to submit Docker models for internal evaluation.
4. **v1.3:** Trusted-execution (TEE/Enclave) infrastructure, cryptographic dataset commitments, and a monthly rotating challenge split to sustain long-term benchmark integrity.

The general pseudo-structure of the repository is available in Appendix A.

3 CASE STUDY

To demonstrate the capabilities of NucBench, we evaluated three leading multimodal LLMs: GPT-4.1 (OpenAI), Claude 3.7 Sonnet (Anthropic), and Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google). These models represent the most widely adopted state-of-the-art systems available at the time of writing. All models were accessed via official APIs, ensuring reproducible parameter control. Evaluations were repeated 50 times for each temperature ($T=0.0, 0.5, 1.0$) to estimate statistical stability. Mean accuracy was calculated as the percentage of correct responses relative to the total number of evaluated items (e.g., questions or images). If the number of correct answers in a test is C_n within a total of Q_n questions in a set, then $A_{m,t}^{(i)}$ denote the accuracy score obtained by model m at temperature t during trial i , where $i=1, \dots, 50$ as shown in Eq. 1. The mean accuracy across all repetitions is then defined by Eq.2 shown below. This value provides a point estimate of expected performance under a given configuration.

$$A_{m,t}^{(i)} = \frac{C_n}{Q_n} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\overline{A_{m,t}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N A_{m,t}^{(i)} \quad (2)$$

In addition to the text based tasks, a series of image analysis tasks related to flow regime analysis were tested. CO₂ and Air flow regimes including bubbly, slug, churn and Taylor flows are included (example images are illustrated in Figure 2). This dataset was generated from experiments conducted in the 140 ft Tower Laboratory at Texas A&M University, utilizing a 5.5 in (140 mm) transparent outer tube concentrically arranged with a 2³/₈ in (60 mm) drill pipe to form a vertical annulus geometry representative of down-hole well configurations [12].

Figure 1. Left: CO₂ Slug flow image. Right: Air bubbly flow

Performance was analyzed separately for text-based and image-based tasks. Deterministic runs ($T = 0$) represent model stability, while higher temperatures introduce controlled randomness. Across all evaluations, GPT-4.1 consistently achieved the highest accuracy, closely matching human-level performance on reactor operator exams ($\sim 95\%$). Claude 3.7 Sonnet maintained lower variance, indicating stronger consistency even when stochasticity increased. The mean accuracy provides a point estimate of expected performance under a given configuration.

Table III. Accuracy of Multimodal LLMs on Text-Based Tasks

Model	T = 0	T = 0.5	T = 1.0
GPT-4.1	95 ± 1.1 %	93 ± 3.0 %	89 ± 4.1 %
Claude 3.7 Sonnet	90 ± 0.5 %	89 ± 5.1 %	82 ± 5.8 %
Gemini 2.5 Pro	87 ± 2.2 %	81 ± 8.1 %	76 ± 8.1 %

The temperature sensitivity of Gemini 2.5 Pro is notably higher, reflecting instability in generation. Varying the LLM sampling temperature allows assessment of how stable, confident, or uncertain a multimodal LLM's outputs are under repeated inference. At low LLM sampling temperature ($T = 0.0$), the model approaches deterministic decoding, producing highly reproducible responses. As the LLM sampling temperature increases, token selection becomes increasingly stochastic, exposing the model's sensitivity to uncertainty and revealing how frequently its predictions shift under identical inputs. This controlled variation enables quantitative evaluation of robustness, reliability, and output variability, and supports selection of appropriate decoding settings for safety-critical nuclear engineering tasks. The LLM sampling temperature is a decoding parameter and is unrelated to physical temperature in nuclear systems.

Relatively consistent accuracy as the temperature is increased results in atypical yet still accurate responses, such as with Claude's relatively flat performance curve, confirming the model's robustness

under moderate variability making it potentially useful for open-ended nuclear tasks such as procedural documentation or qualitative safety review.

Table III. Image-Based Classification Accuracy by Flow Regime ($T = 0$)

Flow Regime	GPT-4.1	Claude 3.7 Sonnet	Gemini 2.5 Pro
Churn	95 %	82 %	59 %
Bubbly	70 %	72 %	65 %
Slug	25 %	40 %	10 %
Taylor	10 %	15 %	8 %

The accuracy of response to qualitative questions was determined through independent nuclear engineering subject-matter experts' scoring of LLM performance in terms of factual accuracy, conceptual completeness, technical clarity, safety and interpretation

For image-based classification, all models correctly identified churn regimes with up to 95 % accuracy at $T = 0$. Performance dropped sharply for Taylor and slug flows, which present more intricate visual structures. Claude 3.7 Sonnet achieved the most balanced accuracy across regimes, while Gemini 2.5 Pro remained the least reliable under stochastic settings. Gemini 2.5 Pro showed greater variability ($\pm 2.2\%$), suggesting residual stochasticity in its outputs even under nominally deterministic decoding, likely attributable to internal sampling or decoding strategies that persist despite a zero sampling temperature.

Analysis across LLM sampling temperature levels reveals that the largest increase in variability occurs when moving from deterministic decoding ($T = 0.0$) to moderately stochastic decoding ($T = 0.5$). Although further increasing the LLM sampling temperature from $T = 0.5$ to $T = 1.0$ was expected to produce an even greater dispersion, the observed increase in standard deviation was comparatively smaller. This suggests that most output instability is introduced once decoding departs from deterministic behavior, with subsequent increases in stochasticity having a diminishing marginal effect on variability.

Across all LLM sampling temperature settings, GPT-4.1 consistently achieved the highest mean accuracy, while Claude 3.7 Sonnet maintained strong consistency with slightly lower mean scores. Gemini 2.5 Pro demonstrated the greatest sensitivity to changes in LLM sampling temperature, exhibiting both larger accuracy degradation and higher variability. When compared to reported human accuracy on the GFE ($\sim 94\text{--}95\%$), GPT-4.1 achieves comparable accuracy under deterministic decoding, followed by Claude 3.7 Sonnet and then Gemini 2.5 Pro.

4 CONCLUSIONS

NucBench establishes the first unified open source, open access, benchmark for assessing multimodal LLMs in nuclear engineering. As a case study, the current version of NucBench is used to evaluate several widely used multimodal LLMs. Results indicate that GPT-4.1 approaches human-level accuracy on deterministic quantitative tasks, Claude 3.7 Sonnet provides optimal stability under moderate stochasticity, and Gemini 2.5 Pro exhibits notable sensitivity to temperature variations. These outcomes reinforce the importance of reproducibility and careful parameter tuning before deploying LLMs in nuclear analysis or operator support roles. Future iterations of NucBench will incorporate domain-specific fine-tuning, explainable AI modules, and uncertainty quantification to align AI behavior with nuclear safety requirements. The authors aim to introduce this public repository with the goal of sharing annotated data for benchmarking and meaningful comparisons for current and future generative AI models.

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APPENDIX A

The NucBench repository is publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/NS3G-UoS/NucBench>). The general structure of the repository's folders and files is outlined below. The datasets folder includes the GFE Operator & Undergraduate Exam Questions as question-answer pairs under the qualitative subfolder, the quantitative subfolder contains answers that are numerical, along with the corresponding units, tolerance and other relevant details to the numerical answer. The images folder contains data for the Two-Phase-Flow Classification task, and the radiation_spectra folder contains data for the Radiation Spectrometry task. The metadata subfolder includes files that help the program point to where each of the subfolders should be and what type of data each subfolder contains. The NucBench folder contains code that loads the dataset


```
NucBench/
├── datasets/
│   ├── qualitative/
│   │   └── qualitative.jsonl      # Q&A pairs (one JSON per line)
│   ├── quantitative/
│   │   └── quantitative.jsonl    # numerals with units/solution/tolerance
│   ├── images/
│   │   ├── thermal_hydraulics/
│   │   │   ├── index.jsonl      # list of images with regime, caption, metadata
│   │   │   ├── bubbly_001.png   # placeholder images (replace with real data)
│   │   │   ├── slug_001.png
│   │   │   └── ...
│   │   └── radiation_spectra/
│   │       ├── images/
│   │       │   └── spectrum_cs137_001.png
│   │       └── outputs/
│   │           └── spectrum_cs137_001.txt # CSV-style: channel,count
│   └── index.jsonl                # pairs image↔output with detector & live_time
├── datasets/metadata/
│   ├── registry.json             # canonical paths to all dataset indices
│   ├── qualitative.schema.json   # JSON schema for QA
│   ├── quantitative.schema.json  # JSON schema for numerals
│   ├── thermal_hydraulics.schema.json # JSON schema for TH images
│   └── radiation_spectrum.schema.json # JSON schema for spectra pairs
├── NucBench/
│   ├── __init__.py
│   ├── loader.py                # import-ready dataset loaders
│   └── utils/
│       └── validate.py          # schema validation (jsonschema)
└── pyproject.toml
```